

OXIDATION OF AROMATIC THIOCARBAMIDES: THE TETRAPHENYL FORMAMIDINE MONOSULPHIDE HYDROBROMIDE

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In its formation by the oxidation of thiocarbamilide by bromine in alcohol, Hugershoff's thiazazole has been shown to be preceded by the formation of tetraphenylformamidine monosulphide which has been isolated as its hydrobromide. Chemistry of this compound has been investigated.

When thiocarbamilide is oxidised with bromine or other oxidising agents (Hugershoff, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3130; 1903, 36, 3121; Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2023; 1929, 462; Sahasrabudhey, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 433; Morton, "The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds", 1946, 2nd impression, p. 434), depending on the conditions of reaction, a thiazazole (I) (structure yet undecided; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 25) or benzothiazole (II) is formed:

(I)

(II)

The formation of these and such other compounds has been believed to be preceded by disulphides of the type obtained from alkyl-substituted thiocarbamides (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1869, 2, 455; Fromm, *Annalen*, 1906, 348, 144; Hector, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1176; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1891, 44, 492; Fromm and Heyder, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3804; McClelland and Warren, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1095) as indeed has recently been confirmed (Sahasrabudhey and Nambury, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1958, Part III, 136; Kurzer and Sanderson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4461; 1959, 1058). Although monosulphides are often formed by the elimination of a sulphur atom from disulphides, and formation of elemental sulphur is observed in the above oxidations, no suggestion has hitherto been made about the formation of such a compound by the decomposition of related disulphides or as a product of oxidation of thiocarbamides.

It has now been found that thiocarbamilide on oxidation with bromine at ordinary temperature or in moderately warm solution affords a yellow crystalline compound, $C_{26}H_{22}N_4BrS$, which from its behaviour appears to be the tetraphenylformamidine monosulphide hydrobromide.

The compound keeps well under dry conditions but in presence of moisture and impurities decomposes. Its behaviour with various reagents can be summarised as follows:

In presence of water it decomposes mainly into hydrobromic acid, phenyl mustard oil and triphenylguanidine.

evaporation of the ethereal extract with ammonia, a solid was obtained. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 154°; these were identified with phenylthiourea by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. The oily product thus proved to be phenyl mustard oil.

The aqueous part on keeping deposited crystals, m.p. 213°, identified with the hydrobromide of triphenylguanidine by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. An aqueous solution of these on basification with ammonia and treatment with picric acid respectively afforded a base, m.p. 144°, and a picrate, m.p. 181°, identified with triphenylguanidine and its picrate.

(ii) *Reaction with ammonia*.—The monosulphide hydrobromide (1 g.) was treated for some time with strong ammonia and filtered. The residue after crystallisation was identified with triphenylguanidine. The filtrate gave crystals of phenylthiourea, m.p. 150°, identified through mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

(iii) *Reaction with acid*.—Monosulphide salt (2 g.) was boiled with 20 c.c. of acidified ethanol (10 parts EtOH in 1.5 parts of conc.HCl) for an hour. The solution first assumed a yellow colour which gradually faded, suggesting the gradual decomposition of the monosulphide in acidified ethanol. On cooling crystals were deposited; these were filtered, washed with chloroform and recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 236°, and showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with carbanilide. Chloroform washings on evaporation gave a colorless residue, which on crystallisation from rectified spirit furnished shining soft plates, m.p. 152°, identified with thiocarbanilide.

The acid-ethanolic filtrate was basified with ammonia when a white precipitate was obtained, which was boiled with water. The aqueous extract afforded phenylthiourea while the residue proved to be a mixture of carbanilide and thiocarbanilide.

The main products of the reaction were thus carbanilide and thiocarbanilide. Phenyl isothiocyanate was also formed in small quantities as indicated by the formation of phenylthiourea on reaction with ammonia.

(iv) *Decomposition at melting point*.—The monosulphide hydrobromide was heated at 150-60° for 15 minutes. The melt after cooling was extracted with petroleum ether and the ethereal extract treated with *p*-toluidine, when a crystalline product was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 143°. This was *N*-phenyl-*N'*-*p*-tolylthiourea, identified through undepressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. The residue left after petroleum ether extraction was boiled with water and recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 232-35°. This was identified with carbanilide. The aqueous extract on basification gave triphenylguanidine, m.p. 146°; picrate, m.p. 181°.

Further Action of Bromine on the Monosulphide Hydrobromide in Ethanol.—A small quantity of the monosulphide salt was dissolved in rectified spirit, acidified with hydrobromic acid. On addition of bromine in dilute ethanol, followed by basification with ammonia, a colorless base was precipitated. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 136°. This was identified with Hegershoff's "thiodiazole," indicating that the monosulphide hydrobromide was oxidised with bromine to furnish the "thiodiazole".

Action of Bromine in Chloroform on the Monosulphide Hydrobromide

The monosulphide hydrobromide (5 g.) was suspended in dry chloroform (50 c.c.) and treated with bromine solution (1 c.c. in 20 c.c. CHCl₃). The salt went into solution generating some warmth. After addition of 17 c.c. (i.e. 2.4 g. bromine) of the bromine solution an

orange-yellow product (6 g.) was thrown down. It was filtered and washed with dry chloroform, dried under vacuum and then at 60-80°, m.p. 145-50°. It could not be crystallised. The product was fairly stable in dry atmosphere. It could be kept unchanged for a few days.

(i) *Estimation of Active Bromine in the Product* (m.p. 145-50°).—As the compound liberated iodine from potassium iodide solution, active bromine was estimated in it by titrating the liberated iodine against a standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The substance (0.2130 g. and 0.2162 g.) was treated separately with 5 c.c. each of 50% aqueous potassium iodide solution, and 10 c.c. of chloroform added. After thorough shaking 5 c.c. of water was added and the liberated iodine titrated against standard thiosulphate (1 c.c. $\equiv$ 0.0064 g. iodine) using starch as indicator; 17.15 c.c. and 17.55 c.c. respectively of thiosulphate were consumed and the equivalent weight values for one equivalent of iodine liberated corresponded with 246.5 and 244.5. Addition of 1 c.c. of HBr had no effect on the titre value. After the titration the chloroform layer was separated and evaporated to dryness. The residue gave out a strong smell of phenyl isothiocyanate. On further examination it was found to contain triphenylguanidine. No thiadiazole could be detected. (Found: N, 7.46, 7.75; total Br, 43.1; active Br, 33.23; equiv. for 1 active Br, 244.5, 246.5. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{23}N_4Br_4S$: N, 7.53; total Br, 43.06; active Br, 32.3%; equiv., 247.6).

(ii) *Reduction of the Perbromide*.—The red perbromide was reduced by aqueous sodium bisulphite when a white crystalline product was obtained, which was acidic to litmus. Eq. wt. of this product determined by titration was 539 (calc. for $C_{26}H_{20}N_4S$, HBr: 501. The higher value is probably due to hydration). The product was dissolved in rectified spirit and a part basified, when a base was precipitated. It was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 136°. Other part was treated with ethanolic picric acid; picrate, m.p. 160-61°. No depression was recorded when mixed with Hegershoff's thiadiazole and its picrate.

Action of Bromine on the Hydrobromide of Hegershoff's Thiadiazole.—The thiadiazole was triturated with HBr (conc.) in a mortar, and this mixture was dissolved in ethanol and filtered in a large quantity of water. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered and dried at 100°. Thiadiazole hydrobromide obtained (0.5 g.) was suspended in dry benzene, and chloroform added till all of it went into solution. Liquid bromine was added till a heavy liquid had separated. On keeping overnight it was crystallised as orange-red crystals, which were dried under vacuum, m.p. 85-95°.

Active bromine was estimated as given above; the values found in two independent experiments were 264.9, 266.4, but these were found to vary (indicating the loss of bromine) on ageing the sample. Thus the product was not as stable as that from the monosulphide. On reduction with sodium bisulphite and subsequent basification it gave back as expected the thiadiazole.

Action of Thionyl Chloride on the Monosulphide

Monosulphide hydrobromide (2 g.) was suspended in dry chloroform (5 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) was gradually added. A white product was thrown down. It was filtered and washed with chloroform. It could not be crystallised. The melting range was 100-130°.

The chloroform filtrate after filtering off the white product was treated with ammonium hydroxide, and evaporated to dryness. The residue was washed with water and carbon disulphide, and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157°. It gave a picrate, m.p. 220-22°. No depression in melting point was observed when these were mixed with 2-phenylaminobenzothiazole and its picrate, respectively.

The white product is acidic to litmus and reactive to ethanolic potassium iodide. The liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate, but concordant results were not obtained.

(i) *Treatment with water.*—The product was suspended in water and kept overnight. The residue, which was strongly acidic, was dissolved in ethanol and treated with alkali, when a product, m.p. 131-33°, was obtained, identified with Hugershoff's thiadiazole.

(ii) *Reduction with sodium bisulphite.*—The product was suspended in water, acidified with HBr, and treated with a strong aqueous solution of sodium bisulphite. A yellow product was obtained. It was dissolved in ethanol, acidified with HBr, and seeded with a few small crystals of the monosulphide salt. After keeping for a few hours yellow crystals, melting after washing with dry chloroform at 153-54°, were obtained. No depression in m.p. was observed when mixed with the original monosulphide salt. This suggests the product, obtained from thionyl chloride and monosulphide, to be an addition product or a complex of SOCl_2 and the monosulphide, which in presence of reducing agents gives back the monosulphide. But in presence of water alone it probably decomposes into SOCl_2 and the monosulphide when oxidation of the latter by the former to Hugershoff's thiadiazole takes place.

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